

THE ESSENCE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND KEY FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION SERVICES

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Abstract. The digital economy represents a transformative phase in global economic development, driven by technological advancements, data proliferation, and interconnectedness. At its core, the digital economy encompasses economic activities enabled by digital technologies, fostering innovation, efficiency, and new business models. It leverages the power of big data, artificial intelligence, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT) to redefine value creation, distribution, and consumption.

The development of communication services plays a pivotal role in this evolution, as they form the backbone of the digital economy. Key features include the rapid expansion of high-speed internet, mobile connectivity, and the integration of advanced technologies like 5G, which enhance real-time communication and data transfer capabilities. Additionally, communication services have increasingly shifted toward platforms and ecosystems, emphasizing user engagement, personalization, and seamless interoperability.

Key words: Digital Economy, Communication Services, Technological Advancements, Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT)

Introduction. The digital economy requires, first of all, the creation of broadband Internet ports, the laying of fiber-optic Internet lines. Taking into account these problems and creating favorable conditions for the development of e-commerce in the country, it is currently relevant.

In recent years, the concept of a digital economy has appeared in the theory and practice of the economy of many countries. It is characterized by the rapid development of digital technologies, the revolution in the information sector and the acceleration of the processes of globalization of the economy.

It is not difficult to notice the impact of the digital economy on all aspects of human life. Currently, the majority of the population of our planet has access to the Internet and can use the services of the digital service economy, social networks, various messengers have already become the main integral part of interpersonal communication.

Literature review. The issues of the development of the digital economy and communication services are being studied by international and domestic scientists. M.A. Morozov and N.S. Morozova have given many opinions on the role and importance of communication services in improving the labor market, as well as on the essence and content of the digital economy [1].

One of our local scientists, O.S. Umarov, also put forward his scientific views on the digital economy and its development trends, which are of particular importance [2].

Analysis and results. The implementation of e-government elements and support for the digital economy are firmly embedded in Uzbekistan's development plan for the near future. This primarily concerns the tasks of further increasing the share of electronic document exchange and gradually transferring a certain part of public services to electronic form through State Service Centers. Telecommunications infrastructure plays an important role in this process.

Interest in the digital economy has grown significantly due to significant changes in society and the economy. Modern technologies and platforms have helped businesses and individuals reduce costs by minimizing personal communication with customers, partners and government organizations, and have

also made it possible to establish communication more quickly and easily. As a result, a digital or electronic economy based on network resources has emerged.

If we talk about the service sector, information technologies solve many everyday tasks, as a result of which large-scale operations are performed faster, cheaper, more conveniently and without intermediaries.

E-commerce, Internet banking and other such modern areas are developing day by day. As a result, in many areas, automated network services (for example, a high-quality website or mobile application) are replacing business intermediaries in order to increase profits.

The digital economy is one of the main priority areas of economic activity in the modern world, the essence of which is to optimize economic processes and increase efficiency through the widespread use of technologies. This type of economy is based on the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) and serves to develop new business models based on the creation, processing and transmission of information.

The **digital economy** represents a paradigm shift in how economic activities are organized, driven by the pervasive adoption of digital technologies. It encompasses the production, distribution, and consumption of goods and services facilitated by digital platforms, networks, and tools. Central to the digital economy is its reliance on data, connectivity, and innovative technologies to drive efficiency, growth, and transformation across industries.

Below is an exploration of the essence of the digital economy and the development of communication services:

Essence of the Digital Economy

1. Definition and Scope:

- The digital economy includes all economic processes enabled by digital technologies, such as e-commerce, digital banking, online education, and digital content creation.

- It relies on digital infrastructure (e.g., broadband internet, cloud computing) and advanced technologies (e.g., AI, IoT, blockchain).

2. Core Components:

- **Digital Platforms:** Online marketplaces (e.g., Amazon, Alibaba), social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, Instagram), and content platforms (e.g., YouTube).

- **Data-Driven Economy:** Data as the primary resource for decision-making, personalization, and automation.

- **Innovation Ecosystem:** Rapid adoption of disruptive technologies fosters continuous innovation and creates new business models.

- **Global Connectivity:** Seamless communication and transactions across borders enable global markets and diverse participation.

3. Key Drivers:

- Advancements in ICT (Information and Communication Technology).

- Widespread internet penetration and mobile device usage.

- Policy frameworks promoting digital infrastructure and innovation.

4. Economic Impact:

- Boosts productivity by automating routine tasks and optimizing supply chains.

- Creates new markets and job opportunities.

- Facilitates financial inclusion through digital payment systems and microfinance platforms.

Development of Communication Services

The evolution of communication services is pivotal to the growth of the digital economy. Communication services have transformed from traditional telephony to sophisticated digital communication platforms.

1. Phases of Development:

- **Traditional Telecommunications (19th–20th Century):**

- Landline telephony dominated, enabling voice communication over long distances.
 - **Mobile Telecommunications (Late 20th Century):**
 - Introduction of mobile phones and SMS revolutionized personal and professional communication.
 - **Internet Era (Late 20th–Early 21st Century):**
 - Email, instant messaging (e.g., WhatsApp), and Voice over IP (VoIP, e.g., Skype) became mainstream.
 - **Digital and Smart Communication (21st Century):**
 - Cloud-based services, 5G networks, and real-time video conferencing (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams) underpin modern communication.

2. Key Features of Modern Communication Services:

- **High-Speed Connectivity:** Advances in 4G, 5G, and fiber-optic technology enable faster data transmission and improved user experiences.
- **Interoperability:** Integration across devices, platforms, and ecosystems ensures seamless communication.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Free or low-cost digital communication tools have replaced expensive traditional methods.
- **Ubiquity:** Mobile-first and always-connected ecosystems allow users to communicate anywhere and anytime.
- **Security and Privacy:** Encryption and secure protocols address concerns over data protection and cyber threats.

3. Role in the Digital Economy:

- Facilitates e-commerce, remote work, telemedicine, and online education.
- Enables businesses to collaborate globally in real-time.
- Drives innovation through faster and more efficient information exchange.

4. Challenges:

- Digital divide between urban and rural areas or developed and developing countries.
- Cybersecurity threats and data breaches.
- Over-reliance on large tech companies, leading to monopolistic practices.

Conclusion. The digital economy thrives on robust communication services that enable connectivity and innovation. As digital technologies evolve, communication services will continue to play a crucial role in shaping economic activities, ensuring inclusivity, and fostering global collaboration. Addressing challenges such as the digital divide and cybersecurity will be critical for sustainable growth in this domain.

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